

had three proline levels: 0, 5, and 10 mM as P₀, P₅, and P₁₀, respectively.

Cultures were placed on a gyrotary shaker (120 rpm) in the dark at 25 ± 1 °C. About 3/4 of the liquid medium was replaced 2x/wk for the first 3-4 wk and weekly thereafter. The smaller calli with light yellow smooth surfaces were selected and transferred to another flask containing fresh medium. The cultures were maintained in the same medium until they were ready for protoplast isolation. See table for media additives.

The addition of proline (5 or 10 mM) in both basal media initiated the growth of secondary calli (indicated by arrows in the figure) on the periphery of the mother callus (MC) as observed in an inverted microscope 4 wk after initiation (fig. a). The secondary calli proliferated well and formed microcalli, which started to separate from the MC after 2 more weeks (fig. b). Such changes were not observed in the absence of proline in basal media

Media additives.

Additive	Concentration ^a (mg/liter)		
	MS	N ₆	R ₂
Nicotinic acid	0.5	0.5	0
Pyridoxine · HCl	0.5	0.5	0
Thiamine · HCl	0.1	1.0	1.0
Myo-inositol	100	0	0
2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid	2.0	1.0	1.0
Sucrose	30000	0	0
Maltose	0	30000	30000
Agarose (Sigma type I)	5500	0	0
Glycine	2.0	2.0	0
Casein hydrolysate	1000	0	0
Proline P ₀	-	0	0
P ₅	-	575.5	575.5
P ₁₀	-	1151.0	1151.0

^aAt pH 5.8.

(fig. c and d). Furthermore, 8 wk after initiation, the MC in the medium without proline started to become brown and hard, stopped growing, and died (fig. e, N₆P₀ and R₂P₀). The microcalli arising

from the MC in medium with proline were still light yellow, smooth, and friable, with about 3-4 mm diameter, and became finer as the culture aged (fig. e, N₆P₁₀, R₆P₁₀, and N₆P₅). ■

Yield potential

Ratoon crop performance in some rice hybrids

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We studied the possibility of using ratoon crops in some F₁ hybrids at the Sukamandi field station during the 1988-

89 wet season. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications in a 3- × 5-m² plot. Hybrids V20 A/IR64, V20 A/IR46 R, V20 A/Krueng-Aceh, V20 A/M66b, V20 A/IR28178, and V20 A/IR25912 and check Dodokan were ratooned by cutting mature stalks at 20 cm above the ground. We topdressed 40 kg N/ha immediately after cutting. The plots were irrigated as needed.

Ratoon hills/m² ranged from 20 for

V20 A/Krueng-Aceh to 25 for V20 A/IR25912. Yields ranged from 0.76 t/ha for V20 A/Krueng-Aceh to 1.27 t/ha for V20 A/IR28178, about 14-22% of the main crop yield (Table 1).

Number of filled spikelets/panicle of the ratoon crop varied from 69.3 for V20 A/Krueng-Aceh to 97.6 for V20 A/IR25912, about 62-92% that of the main crop. The ratoon of hybrid V20 A/IR46 showed the maximum number of panicles/hill at 11.95. The 1,000-grain

Table 1. Maturity, hill number, yield, filled grains/panicle, and stem rot of ratoon and main crops of some rice hybrids. Sukamandi, Indonesia, 1988-89 wet season.^a

Hybrid, check	Maturity (d)		Hills/m ² (no.)		Yield (t/ha)		Filled grains/panicle (no.)		Stem rot ^b	
	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon
V20 A/IR25912	122	62 (51)	25	25 (100)	4.1	1.3 (31)	105.38	97.62 (92) ^a	3	5
V20 A/IR46	120	62 (52)	25	25 (100)	5.1	0.9 (17)	107.20	79.87 (74)	3	5
V20 A/IR64	114	60 (53)	25	25 (100)	4.1	1.1 (27)	104.66	92.35 (88)	3	5
V20 A/Kr. Aceh	114	60 (53)	25	20 (80)	5.6	0.8 (14)	111.20	69.30 (62)	3	7
V20 A/IR28178	113	57 (50)	25	25 (100)	5.9	1.3 (22)	115.85	90.21 (77)	3	5
V20 A/M66b	109	60 (55)	25	25 (100)	5.9	0.8 (14)	115.21	76.20 (66)	3	7
Dodokan	101	53 (52)	25	21 (84)	5.1	0.9 (17)	102.91	80.50 (78)	1	1
LSD (0.05)	3	4			0.4	0.1	15.19	35.58		
CV (%)	1.1	2.7			3.4	2.6	5.7	17.4		

^aFigures in parentheses are % of main crop. ^bBased on *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Table 2. Panicles/hill, panicle exertion, 1000-grain weight, and plant height of ratoon and main crops of some rice hybrids. Sukamandi, Indonesia, 1988-89 wet season.*

Hybrid, check	Panicles/hill (no.)		Panicle exertion (%)		1000-grain weight (g)		Plant height (cm)	
	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon
V20 A/IR25912	13.5	10.00 (74)	104.05	77.65 (74)	26.13	20.07 (76)	116.0	68.6 (59)
V20 A/IR46	13.3	11.95 (89)	105.35	77.03 (73)	22.35	20.42 (92)	104.2	66.6 (64)
V20 A/IR64	12.5	9.35 (74)	105.70	85.79 (81)	28.10	20.34 (73)	111.6	71.7 (64)
V20 A/Kr. Aceh	16.4	11.25 (68)	93.00	86.99 (93)	29.15	22.64 (78)	116.6	73.5 (63)
V20 A/IR28178	13.1	8.80 (67)	109.51	80.83 (73)	26.05	20.24 (78)	113.5	64.7 (57)
V20 A/M66b	14.9	10.50 (70)	111.20	78.33 (70)	28.05	21.07 (76)	118.4	71.0 (60)
Dodokan	15.7	10.45 (66)	113.50	71.35 (63)	28.55	23.25 (82)	104.2	72.2 (69)
LSD (0.05)	3.6	3.81	7.55	2.98	5.66	6.58	3.7	3.6
CV (%)	10.4	14.7	2.9	1.5	8.7	12.9	1.3	2.1

*Figures in parentheses are % of main crop.

weight of the ratoon crop was about 76-78% of that of the main crop. Plant height ranged from 64.7 cm for V20 A/IR28178 to 73.5 cm for V20 A/Krueng-Aceh (Table 2). *Helminthosporium sigmoideum*

incidence on the hybrids was 6-50%, while that on Dodokan was only 1%. V20 A/IR25912, V20 A/IR64, and V20 A/IR28178 yielded significantly more than the check.

F₁ hybrids offer some advantages for use in the ratoon crop. In breeding programs for hybrid rice, emphasis should be given to selecting parents with good ratooning ability. ■

Yield and yield components of some new rice hybrids derived from IR58025 A and IR62829 A in Indonesia

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We evaluated 15 IRRI rice hybrids of which eight were derived from IR58025 A and seven from IR62829 A, three Indonesian hybrids derived from IR62829 A, IR64, and Way-Seputih in a yield trial during the 1991 dry season in Kuningan. Single seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 3- × 5-m² plots with three replications. Plots

were fertilized with 135-50-50 kg NPK/ha. IR58025 A/IR10198, IR58025 A/IR15324, and IR58025 A/Pusa 150 yielded as much as IR64 and Way-Seputih. The hybrids had more unfilled grains/panicle than IR64 (see table). ■

Yield components of some new rice hybrids. Kuningan, Indonesia, 1991 dry season.

Hybrid, variety	Yield (t/ha)	Maturity (d)	1000-grain wt (g)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)	Panicles/hill (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Plant height (cm)	Unfilled grains/panicle (no.)
IR64	5.9	135	20.41	61.11	16.9	19.8	68.9	13.42
IR58025 A/IR10198	5.9	136	21.59	81.28	16.23	20.6	77.7	24.20
IR58025 A/IR15324	5.4	127	22.61	74.33	14.96	20.3	77.1	24.81
Way-Seputih	5.2	136	22.62	88.34	12.53	16.9	77.4	24.13
IR58025 A/Pusa 150	5.2	130	21.40	79.04	15.43	18.2	74.8	36.57
IR58025 A/IR40750	5.0	141	20.24	79.97	14.9	18.2	81.3	45.46
IR62829 A/Pusa 150	4.9	127	19.43	44.19	19.4	16.6	66.0	23.5
IR58025 A/IR37839	4.7	136	21.34	63.14	16.23	19.6	78.4	23.65
IR62829 A/IR28238	4.7	127	18.02	71.18	15.2	16.5	73.9	32.70
IR62829 A/IR40750	4.5	130	19.11	46.70	19.93	17.9	67.8	28.29
IR58025 A/IR54742	4.4	143	21.92	75.90	11.23	20.4	86.0	54.15
IR62829 A/M66b	4.1	127	20.22	53.50	16.26	17.2	69.6	31.17
IR62829 A/IR15324	4.0	127	20.65	70.04	14.17	18.7	75.5	31.33
IR62829 A/IR10198	3.9	127	19.62	74.53	11.43	18.2	74.5	36.50
IR62829 A/IR54	3.4	136	21.31	39.49	19.7	18.2	67.8	32.0
IR62829 A/IR29723	1.8	130	21.50	26.02	17.13	16.0	68.4	64.55
IR62829 A/IR64	1.7	130	20.52	28.47	18.53	18.2	67.4	39.80
IR58025 A/IR29723	1.6	141	23.74	45.58	13.4	18.6	75.9	74.95
IR58025 A/IR32809	1.1	136	23.78	68.49	13.13	18.8	74.2	57.6
IR62829 A/IR32809	1.0	130	22.98	25.38	17.36	18.3	62.7	44.03
CV (%)	14.0	-	3.8	20.0	16.9	8.5	3.4	26.9
LSD (0.05)	0.9	-	1.29	15.38	4.28	2.52	4.08	16.13

An innovative approach to improve rice yield

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In areas where rice production has stagnated and demand continues to increase, new approaches are needed to stimulate production. We applied plant growth regulators (PGRs) to rice in an attempt to improve yield.

The 100-m² experimental and control plots had thirty 10-m rows with 0.2-m spacing between rows and 1-m spacing between plots, replicated three times. High-yielding PR106 seeds, treated with streptomycin and methoxy-ethyl-mercury chloride, were sown in mid-May and transplanted in late Jun. The foliar sprays of PGRs (Table 1) were applied weekly from early Aug to Oct using the manufacturers' recommended dose. The control plot was sprayed weekly with quantities of water equivalent to the recommended doses.